

Thermal Stability of Chalcogenide Perovskites

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Supporting Information Placeholder

ABSTRACT: Chalcogenide perovskites (CPs) have recently attracted interest as a class of materials with practical potential in optoelectronics and have been suggested as a more thermally stable alternative to intensely studied halide perovskites (HPs). Here we report a comparative study of the thermal stability of representative HPs, MAPbI₃ (MA = CH₃NH₃⁺, methylammonium) and CsPbI₃ and a series of CPs with compositions BaZrS₃, β-SrZrS₃, BaHfS₃, SrHfS₃. Changes in the crystal structure, chemical composition, and optical properties upon heating in air up to 800 °C were studied using Thermogravimetric Analysis, Temperature Dependent X-ray Diffraction, Energy dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy and Diffuse Reflectance Spectroscopy. While HPs undergo phase transitions and thermally decompose at temperatures below 300 °C, the CPs show no changes in crystal phase or composition when heated up to at least 450 °C. At 500 °C CPs oxidize on time scales of several hours, forming oxides and sulphates. The structural origins of the higher thermal and phase stability of the CPs are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Halide Perovskites (HPs) have over the past two decades attracted a great deal of attention due to their record-breaking performance as active components of solar cells¹ and other optoelectronic applications.² However, the development of applications of HPs has been impeded by their limited thermal and chemical stability³ as well as concerns about the toxicity of the lead ion. Search for solutions that would address these challenges is currently an area of active research.

Structurally related Chalcogenide Perovskites (CPs), crystalline solids with composition ABX₃, where A, B, are metal cations and X = S²⁻, Se²⁻, have recently been suggested as a possible alternative with the potential to address the limitations of HPs.⁴ Theoretical⁵ and experimental^{5a, 6} studies suggest that CPs have optical and electronic properties similar to the HPs and can be prepared without the use of toxic elements. Initial studies of thermal stability of BaZrS₃ and β-SrZrS₃ powders⁷ concluded that CPs have an excellent thermal stability in air to at least 550 °C and that the BaZrS₃ films show better thermal and chemical stability than HP MAPbI₃ (MA = CH₃NH₃⁺). Here, we report a complementary comparative study of thermal stability of four CPs: BaZrS₃, β-SrZrS₃, BaHfS₃, SrHfS₃ and two representative HPs, MAPbI₃ and CsPbI₃. The results for related non-perovskite, needle-like phases of α-EuZrS₃ and α-SrZrS₃ are included in the Supporting Information (SI). (Note: in cases when the CPs are known to crystalize in two crystal phases, needle-like (NH₄CdCl₃-type) and distorted perovskite (GdFeO₃-type), consistent with prior literature, we denote these throughout the text as α- and β- or NL and DP, respectively. A further discussion on the CP notation is given in later sections and in footnote 25).

The changes in the crystal phase, chemical composition and optical

properties of CP and HP powders heated in air up to 800 °C were investigated using Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), temperature dependent X-ray diffraction (XRD), Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) and Diffuse reflectance spectroscopy. The results quantitatively show the difference since in thermal stability of HPs and CPs, reveal the mechanism and dynamics of the thermal decomposition and its effects on the optical properties of CPs. The factors responsible for the difference in the thermal stability of the HPs and CPs are examined and analyzed.

RESULTS

Structural characteristics. Scheme 1 shows crystal structures of a representative HP, MAPbI₃,⁸ and CP, BaZrS₃.⁹ Both materials belong to the perovskite family of crystalline solids and have similar structure, but there are important differences. MAPbI₃ crystallizes in three different crystal phases within a relatively narrow temperature range 160-330 K.¹⁰ At low temperature T < 160 K (-113 °C) to most stable phase is γ-phase (orthorhombic lattice, *Pnma* space group), at intermediate temperature, T = 160-330 K (-113 °C to

Scheme 1. Crystal structure of the MAPbI₃, β-phase (tetragonal, *I4/mcm*); view along (-110) direction (a) view along (001) direction (b) and BaZrS₃, distorted perovskite phase (orthorhombic, *Pnma*); view along (010) direction (c) and view along (101) direction (d). The relative sizes of ions and bond lengths are shown in scale. The ionic radii were taken from ref. 13.

57 °C), β -phase (tetragonal, $I4/mcm$), and the high temperature, $T > 330$ K (57 °C), α -phase (cubic, $Pm\bar{3}m$). Within the MAPbI_3 crystal, the smaller Pb^{2+} ions (ionic radius, $r_B = 1.03$ Å) are octahedrally coordinated by six large Γ ions ($r_X = 2.2$ Å), with the MA^+ cations ($r_A = 2.17$ Å) centrally located in the space between the corner sharing octahedra.¹¹ In the β -phase (Scheme 1 (a) (b)), stable at room temperature, the Pb-I bond lengths are 3.17-3.18 Å and Pb-I-Pb angle 164 – 180°. When looking along the direction of (-110) plane (panel (a)), the PbI_6 octahedrons in the neighboring layers are rotated with respect to each other by 16.4 deg, while they are aligned when viewed along the (001) direction (panel (b)). The structural octahedral factor, defined as $\mu_O = r_B/r_X = 0.46$ and Goldschmidt's tolerance factor,¹² $t_F = (r_A + r_X)/\sqrt{2}(r_B + r_X) = 0.957$.

In contrast, BaZrS_3 is known to crystallize in two crystal phases: a low temperature, $T < 893$ K (520 °C) distorted perovskite phase (orthorhombic, $Pnma$) and a high temperature, $T > 933$ K (560 °C) tetragonal, $I4_1/acd$ phase.¹³ Within the structure, the small Zr^{4+} cations ($r_B = 0.72$ Å) are octahedrally coordinated by six larger S^{2-} anions ($r_X = 1.84$ Å). The Ba^{2+} cations ($r_A = 1.61$ Å) are located within the space between the corner sharing octahedra. Although, at room temperature BaZrS_3 forms a different crystal lattice (orthorhombic) than MAPbI_3 , (tetragonal) the views along the (010) direction (Scheme 1, (c)) and (101) (Scheme 1 (d)) show the similarities between the crystal structures of the two compounds. There are also clear differences. The Zr-S bond lengths are 2.55-2.56 Å, significantly shorter than Pb-I bond lengths in MAPbI_3 . As a result, the BaZrS_3 forms much tighter structure (Zr-Zr distance between the two neighboring octahedra is 4.98-4.99 Å) than MAPbI_3 (Pb-Pb distance is 6.28-6.36 Å). Like MAPbI_3 , when viewed along the (010) direction (panel (c)) in BaZrS_3 , the ZrS_6 octahedrons in the neighboring layers are rotated. In the case of BaZrS_3 the rotation along the view axis is 22.3°. In addition, in BaZrS_3 the octahedrons are tilted with respect to the view direction. The view along the (101) direction (panel (d)) shows that in BaZrS_3 , although aligned in neighboring layers, the ZrS_6 octahedrons are rotated and tilted with respect to each other in the same layer, unlike the MAPbI_3 . The structural octahedral factor $\mu_O = 0.391$ and Goldschmidt's tolerance factor $t_F = 0.952$. The structural characteristics of other compositions studied in the present work are summarized in Supporting Information, Tables TS1 and TS2.

Materials preparation. The HPs MAPbI_3 and CsPbI_3 were prepared using procedures described previously,¹⁴ with small modifications. Briefly, methylammonium iodide (MAI) was prepared by dropwise addition of methylamine to an excess of cold HI. The mixture was stirred for 2 hrs. in an ice bath and for 12 hrs. at room temperature. The MAI was precipitated from the solution by addition of diethyl ether, collected by vacuum filtration and purified by recrystallization from ethanol. The MAI was then co-dissolved with PbI_2 in dimethylformamide by stirring at 70 °C. After stirring for 120 min. the solvent was evaporated at 110 °C, resulting in formation of a black powder of MAPbI_3 (tetragonal β -phase). CsPbI_3 was prepared from CsI and PbI_2 dissolved in DMSO at 70 °C under vigorous stirring. The temperature was then increased to 80 °C to evaporate the solvent. This resulted in formation of yellow powder of CsPbI_3 (δ -phase).

The CPs, BaZrS_3 , β - SrZrS_3 , BaHfS_3 and SrHfS_3 were synthesized following a procedure described in our recent work.¹⁵ Briefly, a ternary oxide (BaZrO_3 , SrZrO_3 , BaHfO_3 or SrHfO_3) was thoroughly mixed with solid sulfur and a small excess of boron in an agate mortar and pestle. The mixed powder was loaded into a quartz tube with an inner diameter of 15 mm. The tube was evacuated, and flame sealed, forming a quartz reaction ampule. The ampule with sample was heated in a box furnace at 1000 °C for 36 h. The typical heating rate was 5 °C/min with a holding time of 5 hrs. at 300 °C and 5 hrs. at 600 °C, and the cooling rate was 5 °C/min. After the cooling, the ampule was opened at ambient

conditions. The product removed from the reaction ampule was transferred into a beaker and sonicated for 10 min with a small amount (~20 mL) of HPLC-grade methanol to remove any soluble byproducts (e.g., B_2O_3). More details regarding the preparation of materials are included in the experimental section.

The XRD patterns of prepared HPs and CPs are summarized in Figure 1 (the XRD patterns for the non-perovskite needle-like (NL) phases α - SrZrS_3 and α - EuZrS_3 are shown in SI, Fig.S1). The analysis of the XRD patterns did not reveal any impurities in any of the samples. In the case of CsPbI_3 the figure shows the XRD pattern of the yellow, orthorhombic δ -phase.

Thermogravimetric (TGA) analysis. Figure 2 shows the results of the differential thermogravimetric analysis (DTA) of the HPs (panel (a)) and CPs (panel (b)). In the experiments the samples were heated in air. The results for MAPbI_3 (panel (a), blue traces) show that an initial mass loss is observed in 250–290 °C range and occurs in two steps. In a first step, ~21% mass is lost in the range 290–420 °C. In the second step, additional ~60% of the original mass is lost in the range 420–750 °C. These observations are consistent with previous studies. Dualeh et al.¹⁶ and Liu et al.¹⁷ attributed the first mass loss to the release of HI and CH_3NH_2 , consistent with the Eq. (1a) below. The second step was attributed to the thermal

Figure 1. Powder X-ray diffraction patterns (blue traces) of the CPs prepared from the corresponding ABO_3 oxides and the reference literature patterns (orange traces) of the CPs obtained from the ICDD database. The pattern shown for the CsPbI_3 is of the non-perovskite δ -phase.

Figure 2. Mass change and DTA of prepared HPs (a) CPs (b) as a function of temperature. Label Exo indicates an exothermic process. The heating rate was 8 °C/min.

decomposition of PbI_2 . In later work, Juarez-Perez et al.,¹⁸ performed TGA measurement coupled with mass spectrometry (MS) of MAPbI_3 single crystal in an inert He atmosphere and in the mixture of He/ O_2 and/or moisture mixtures. They observed that the initial mass loss in the temperature range 290–400 °C was associated with release of NH_3 and CH_3I , regardless of the atmosphere, consistent with Eq. 1b. These results were later supported by Ma et al.¹⁹ In the inert atmosphere the additional mass loss, starting around 400 °C was attributed to PbI_2 sublimation (1c). In the experiments with the He/ O_2 mixture, the PbI_2 was found to partially oxidize to Pb_xO_y , consistent with Eq. (1d).

In the case of CsPbI_3 (Fig. 2a, green traces) we observed the initial mass loss around 350–400 °C. The mass loss also occurred in two stages with the initial ~40% mass loss completed at ~600 °C. Additional ~20% mass loss was observed in the 600–800 °C range. These results are also consistent with the literature. Dastidar et al.²⁰ studied the phase transition and thermal degradation of CsPbI_3 using absorption spectroscopy and TGA analysis under an N_2 atmosphere. They found that at ca. 305 °C CsPbI_3 undergoes phase transition from the yellow, orthorhombic non-perovskite δ -phase to a black, cubic, metastable, perovskite α -phase. This phase transition was not detected in the TGA. The initial chemical decomposition of CsPbI_3 was observed at ~400 °C with the first mass loss assigned to a partial loss of PbI_2 due to sublimation. This was confirmed by the transmittance spectra where a rapid loss of transmittance in 420–450 °C temperature range was attributed to a formation of a transient PbI_2 -depleted intermediate. Any mass and spectral changes above 450 °C were attributed to the sublimation of remaining PbI_2 . The process of CsPbI_3 thermal decomposition in the absence of air is summarized by Eq. (2):

In the presence of air, at high temperature in addition to sublimation of PbI_2 may also partially oxidize, as shown in Eq. (1c). The results of our TGA studies for BaZrS_3 , β - SrZrS_3 , BaHfS_3 and SrHfS_3 are summarized in Fig. 2b (see SI Fig. S2 for the α - SrZrS_3 and α - EuZrS_3 NL compositions). The results show that no

significant mass changes are observed for any of the CPs to temperature ~450 °C. Above this temperature, the observed mass variations depend on the heating rate. At 8 °C/min. no significant mass variations are observed for any CP up to ~600 °C. Our results are in agreement with previous TGA studies of BaZrS_3 and β - SrZrS_3 by Niu et al.^{7a} In the study, the authors concluded that the two compounds are stable in air up to ~600 °C. At higher temperatures, the TGA showed no appreciable weight loss, only gradual weight gain, which was attributed to the reaction of CPs with oxygen and formation of metal sulfates. However, as shown in SI Fig. S3, we observed that at heating rate 1 °C/min, starting from ~450 °C, all CPs (except for SrHfS_3) show an initial small increase in mass, followed by a drop in mass above 500 °C and then again mass increase above ~600 °C.

The above observations suggest that the oxidation of the studied CPs proceeds in multiple closely following steps. The initial small mass increase in the 450–500 °C is attributed to the oxygen adsorption on the CP surface. The next steps are attributed to the decomposition of the CP and oxidation of the products. One possibility is that ABX_3 first decomposes into its binary sulfides BS_2 and AS , which subsequently oxidize to the respective oxide, BO_2 and sulphate ASO_4 . This mechanism is, however, inconsistent with our high-temperature XRD studies (see following section), where we found that when heated under Argon atmosphere to temperatures up to 700 °C, CPs have shown no sign of degradation (see SI Fig. S4). This indicates that the exposure to air plays a key role in the thermal degradation of the CPs. Based on this, we propose a two-step CP oxidation mechanism summarized in Eqs. (3a-b), shown for the case of BaZrS_3 :

Both reactions are highly thermodynamically favorable ($\Delta_r H^\circ(3a) = -1090$ kJ/mol, $\Delta_r H^\circ(3b) = -1013$ kJ/mol). The reaction (3a) is accompanied with a mass loss while the reaction (3b) is accompanied with a mass gain, with the net effect of ~10% mass gain. The differences in the shape of the TGA Δm traces for various CPs at slow heating rates can be attributed to different rates of reactions (3a) and (3b). In cases when reaction (3a) is significantly faster than (3b), slow TGA scans may reveal a mass drop followed by a mass gain, as observed for several CPs in traces collected at heating rate 1 °C/min (SI Fig. S3). Since both reactions are highly exothermic, the DTA peaks

Figure 3. HT XRD patterns of HPs MAPbI₃ (a), CsPbI₃ (b) recorded in the temperature range RT–500 °C and CPs BaZrS₃ (c), β-SrZrS₃ (d), BaHfS₃ (e), SrHfS₃ (f), recorded in the temperature range 400–800 °C. All measurements were performed in air. The heating rate between the data collections was 8 °C/min. During the data collection, 60 s, the temperature was held constant.

represent the sum of heats released from both reactions. The differences in the oxidation kinetics may contribute to the observed differences in the shape of the peaks. A more detailed discussion of the CP oxidation is included in the following sections.

Temperature-dependent XRD. A more detailed information about the structural and chemical changes induced in HPs and CPs at elevated temperatures was obtained from temperature dependent XRD measurements. The results are summarized in Fig. 3. Panel (a) shows the changes observed in the XRD patterns of the MAPbI₃ from RT to 500 °C. The RT data show XRD pattern characteristic of the β-phase, with characteristic peaks at 2theta of 20, 23.5, 24.5, 28.5, 31.9, 35.04, 40.54, 43.14, and 50.30°. Consistent with the earlier reports in literature, this pattern is stable up to ~50–60 °C. In this temperature range, peak at 23.5° gradually disappears and new peaks appear at 2theta of 28.2, and 31.6°. These changes are attributed to transition from tetragonal β-phase to the cubic α-phase. A second significant change in the XRD pattern is observed in the range 290–300 °C, with all of the characteristic features of the α-phase disappearing. This change is attributed to the start of the thermal decomposition of the MAPbI₃, consistent with processes shown in Eq. 1.

The temperature dependent XRD of CsPbI₃ (Fig. 3b) shows that this HP maintains the XRD pattern observed at RT (Fig. 1) up to ~305 °C, with the most dominant characteristic peaks at 2theta of 23, 26, 31, and 37°. At this temperature a dramatic

change in the XRD pattern is observed, attributed to phase transition from δ-CsPbI₃ to α-CsPbI₃. Starting at about ~350–370 °C the characteristic XRD pattern of α-CsPbI₃ starts to fade away and new XRD pattern appears, attributed to the formation of thermal decomposition intermediates and CsI, consistent with the processes described by Eq. 2.

Fig. 3c shows that BaZrS₃ retains the XRD pattern observed at RT (Fig. 1), with the main characteristic peaks at 2theta of 25, 37, 43 and 51 ° up to ~520 °C. Above this temperature the latter three peaks show a clear splitting, which is detectable up to ~600 °C. In our recent study,¹³ where we investigated the temperature-dependent XRD of BaZrS₃ under an inert atmosphere, we have shown that these changes are associated with the phase transition from the distorted perovskite phase (orthorhombic, *Pnma*) to a pseudo-cubic (tetragonal, *I4₁/acd*) phase. In the air-exposed samples studied here, the corresponding changes in the XRD patterns are partially obstructed and distorted by the BaZrS₃ oxidation, which is detected as an emergence of new set of peaks, with features near 20, 22.5, 24.5, 25.5, 26.5, 28.35, 29.98, 31, 32.3, and 42 °, with the onsets in the range of ~520–570 °C. As a result of the BaZrS₃ oxidation, the features associated with the *Pnma* and the *I4₁/acd* phases are completely undetectable by ~670 °C. As the main products of oxidation, we identified ZrO₂ and BaSO₄ (see Fig. 4).

Fig. 3d shows that β-SrZrS₃ retains the RT XRD pattern (Fig. 1) up to ~570 °C, with the main characteristic peaks at 2theta of

Figure 4. Powder XRD patterns (blue traces) of CPs indicated in the legends after heating to 800 °C in air and the reference patterns (orange traces) of the corresponding oxides and sulphates obtained from the ICDD database.

25.5, 36 and 46°. Above this temperature a new set of peaks starts emerging at around 30.2 and 50 degrees, attributed to the formation of ZrO_2 . Additional peaks near 26.56, 27.70, 43.60, and 44.34° appear at ~720 °C. These new peaks are attributed to $SrSO_4$ (see Fig. 4). Simultaneously, the peaks associated with the β - $SrZrS_3$ gradually decrease in intensity. They are completely undetectable by around 730 °C.

Fig. 3e shows that $BaHfS_3$ retains the RT XRD pattern (Fig. 1) up to ~420 °C. At ~420 °C the peaks at 2theta of 18, 36, 44.5, and 52° show clear splitting, indicating an onset of a phase transition. A closer examination of the individual XRD patterns in the temperature range 400-450°C shows that the changes in the diffraction patterns near the 2theta of 36° are very similar to the changes observed for $BaZrS_3$ in the temperature range 490–590 °C (see SI Fig. S5). A detailed analysis of the XRD patterns confirmed that the observed changes are due to the transition from the distorted perovskite phase (orthorhombic, $Pnma$) to the pseudo-cubic (tetragonal, $I4_1/acd$) phase. The obtained lattice parameters are included in SI, Table TS2. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first experimental observation of the phase transition for this material. Above ~490 °C the peaks near 25, 36, 44.5, and 52.5° start to gradually decrease in intensity. Simultaneously, a new set of peaks starts emerging at 2theta of 22.5, 26.5, 28.5, 30, 32.5, 34.5 and 42.5 degrees, which we attribute to the formation of oxidation by-products. The peaks at 30, 32.5, 34.5 are attributed to

Figure 5. Comparison of the short-term thermal stability of the prepared HPs and CPs at 100 °C (a) 300 °C (b), and 500 °C (c) in air. The data points represent a total area of multiple XRD peaks associated with a particular phase, relative to the total area of the same peaks in the as prepared sample. In cases where the results were the same for multiple phases (0%, 100%) the curves were slightly offset for clarity.

monoclinic and cubic phases of HfO_2 . The peaks at 22.5, 26.5, 28.5 and 42.5 degrees are attributed to the formation of $BaSO_4$ (see Fig. 4). The peaks associated with $BaHfS_3$ are completely undetectable at ~560 °C.

The temperature dependent XRD of $SrHfS_3$ in Fig. 3f shows that the pattern observed at RT (Fig. 1), with the characteristic peaks at 2theta of 18, 20.5, 25, 25.5, 26, 36.5, 41 and 42°, is retained up to ~550 °C. Above this temperature the characteristic peaks rapidly decrease in intensity and new distinct peaks start to emerge. The new peaks near 28 and 35° are attributed to the formation of a monoclinic HfO_2 . A new peak near 31° is attributed to the formation of $SrHfO_3$. The peaks emerging around ~580 °C at 27 and 33° are attributed to the formation of $SrSO_4$. The peaks associated with $SrHfS_3$ are completely undetectable above ~570 °C.

We note that prominent peaks in patterns of $BaHfS_3$, $SrHfS_3$, β - $SrZrS_3$ at 2theta around 39, and 46° are attributed to platinum

Figure 6. Diffuse reflectance of CPs: as-prepared (red traces), after heating in air at 100 °C for one week (green traces) and after heating in air at 800 °C for 30 min (blue traces) for BaZrS₃ (a), SrZrS₃ (b), BaHfS₃ (c) and SrHfS₃ (d). The DR spectra of the reference ABO₃ samples are shown as black traces for comparison. The insets show the photographs of the CP pellets, overlaid with the corresponding DR spectra. The dashed lines represent the optimal band gap (1.72 eV) for a high energy band gap material for a two-junction tandem solar cell.²²

used as the heating strip in the temperature-dependent XRD measurements.

Analysis of the products of thermal decomposition. The products of the thermal decomposition generated upon heating of the HPs and CPs to 800 °C in air were analyzed “post-mortem” using XRD and EDS. In the case of MAPbI₃, in the XRD patterns of the decomposition product we identified two separate phases of PbO (orthorhombic and tetragonal) as well as Pb₃O₄. In the case of CsPbI₃, the XRD analysis also revealed the presence of the two PbO phases and CsI. These results are consistent with the decomposition mechanisms discussed in the previous section and summarized in Eqs. 1 and 2.

The results of the XRD study of the CPs decomposition products are summarized in Fig. 4 (see SI Fig. S6 for the α -SrZrS₃ and α -EuZrS₃ NL phases). The XRD analysis shows that in all studied cases the products are consisting of a mixture of BO₂ (B = Zr⁴⁺ or Hf⁴⁺) oxides in one or more crystal phases and the ASO₄ (A = Ba²⁺ or Sr²⁺) sulphates. No peaks of remaining ABS₃ ternary sulfides were detected in any of the XRD patterns. The XRD results are consistent with the results of the EDS study shown in SI Fig. S7. A comparison of the EDS spectra of the as prepared and samples annealed at 800 °C for 30 min. shows a dramatic reduction in the relative amount of sulfur and a significant increase in the oxygen content in the latter, consistent with the formation of sulphates. Our results are also consistent with the previous Raman, TGA and EDS studies of BaZrS₃ and β -SrZrS₃ reported by Niu et. al.^{7a} While the details of the reaction mechanism and the dynamics of formation of various reaction intermediates can be complex, we conclude that the process of thermal decomposition of the studied CPs can be in a simplified form summarized by Eq. 4.

Dynamics of thermal decomposition. To better understand the dynamics of the thermal degradation of HPs and CPs, we performed short-term, time dependent XRD measurements at 100, 300, and 500 °C. In the experiment the XRD patterns were collected in 10 min intervals for 1 hr. at each temperature. Each XRD pattern was analyzed in terms of the content of the starting material where the areas of at least three main characteristic peaks were integrated. The variations in the content of an ABX₃ phase, relative to as-prepared material measured at room temperature ($W_{\text{ABX}_3} = 100\%$) are plotted in Fig. 5 (see SI Fig. S8 for α -SrZrS₃ and α -EuZrS₃ NL phases).

As shown in panel (a), at 100 °C the MAPbI₃ was observed only in its cubic α -phase ($W_{\text{ABX}_3} = 100\%$) while no peaks of tetragonal β -phase were detected ($W_{\text{ABX}_3} = 0\%$). This is expected because of the β - to α - transition, taking place at ~ 50 – 60 °C, as discussed in the previous section. Similarly, CsPbI₃ was observed only in its non-perovskite δ -phase ($W_{\text{ABX}_3} = 100\%$), while no presence of the cubic, perovskite α -phase was detected ($W_{\text{ABX}_3} = 0\%$). All CPs were detected as distorted perovskites, with no measurable changes in the XRD patterns during the 1 hr. of heating.

In addition to the short-term stability study summarized in Fig. 5, the stability of the HPs and CPs was also investigated in a long-term experiment. In the experiment the perovskite powders were heated in air at 100 °C for 1 week and the XRD patterns were collected every 24 hrs. We were unable to detect any differences between the before and after XRD patterns for any of the materials.

At 300 °C (Fig. 5 (b)) the MAPbI₃ was not detected in the XRD pattern, indicating that it has completely decomposed prior to reaching the target temperature. In the case of CsPbI₃, both δ - ($W_{\text{ABX}_3} \sim 30$ – 50%), and α - ($W_{\text{ABX}_3} \sim 50$ – 80%) phases are detected during the initial measurement. The amount of δ -phase

Figure 7. Thermal stability map for HPs and CPs studied in the present work. The chemical equations show thermodynamically favorable processes that may contribute to decomposition of the HPs and CPs. The reactions that can take place in air are shown in blue.

rapidly decreases, with only about 5% detected after 1 hr. The amount of α -phase increases during the first 10 min, as the δ -to α -phase transition takes place. After the initial 10 min the amount of α -phase slowly decreases with ~50% of the phase detected after 1 hr. In the case of CPs, no measurable changes were observed in the XRD patterns during the 1 hr. of heating.

At 500 °C (Fig. 5 (c)) no peaks of HPs are detected in the XRD patterns. For the CPs we observe a gradual decomposition in all cases. The full degradation is observed on the time scale of about two to several hours. The kinetics of the decomposition of the CPs were found to be similar, with somewhat slower decomposition observed for SrHfS₃. Our analysis of the samples used in the short-term thermal stability experiment revealed that in the case of SrHfS₃ the maximum of the grain size distribution is shifted to larger values compared to the other CPs (SI Fig. S9). As for larger grains the oxidation is expected to proceed more slowly due to a smaller surface to volume ratio, we conclude that the slower degradation kinetics observed in the case of SrHfS₃ is likely mostly related to the larger sizes of its grains.

Effect of heating on optical properties. The effect of heating on the optical properties of CPs was investigated by diffuse reflectance (DR) spectroscopy. The results are summarized in Fig. 6.²¹ The figure shows the comparison of the reflectance (as 1-R%) for the as-prepared ABX₃ samples, samples heated at 100 °C in air for 1 week (168 hrs.), sample heated 800 °C in air for 30 min. and a control ABO₃ sample. The CP samples were heated as powders. All sample powders were pressed into ~2 mm thick pellets prior to the DR measurement. The DR spectra of the as-prepared samples show a distinct onset of the signal in the range 500–800 nm. Using the reflectance signal as an approximation for the absorbance, we estimate bandgaps for the BaZrS₃, β -SrZrS₃, BaHfS₃ and SrHfS₃ to be 1.81, 2.01, 1.89, and 2.25 eV, respectively (SI Fig. S10). This is consistent with prior literature reports.^{6a, 22} The DR spectra of the samples heated at 100 °C are very similar to the as-prepared samples, with the high reflectance onsets appearing at the same energy as in the fresh samples. Small differences in the

magnitude of the reflectance that can be noted in the NIR region is attributed to small variations in the surface properties of the pellet and/or differences in the grain sizes of the powders used for the pellet preparation. Following the heating of the CPs at 800 °C the sharp band-edge onsets are shifted to higher energies (SrZrS₃ and SrHfS₃) or disappear altogether (BaZrS₃ and BaHfS₃) and a 50 – 60% increase in reflectance (decrease in 1 -R%) is observed. These changes are consistent with the oxidation of the CPs as discussed in previous section. The DR spectra of the oxidized ABS₃ CPs are similar to but not identical with the control ABO₃ oxide samples. We attribute this difference primarily to the presence of ASO₄ sulfates, identified in the oxidation products by XRD analysis (see Fig. 4). The effects of the heating on the optical properties of CPs were found to be the similar for the NL ternary chalcogenides α -SrZrS₃ and α -EuZrS₃, as shown in SI Fig. S11.

DISCUSSION

Fig. 7 shows a thermal stability map of the HPs and CPs studied in this work. When comparing the two classes of materials, there are several apparent differences. First, when heated at ambient pressure in air, both HPs thermally decompose at temperatures below 400 °C. In the case of MAPbI₃ the first stage of decomposition is observed in 250-290 °C. In contrast, under the same conditions no evidence of thermal decomposition of CPs was observed until ~450 °C, when they start oxidizing into binary oxides (BO₂) and sulphates (ASO₄). Second, below ~300 °C (temperature range relevant for typical optoelectronic applications) the HPs undergo one or more phase transitions. In the case of MAPbI₃ the RT stable tetragonal β -phase (used in high-performance solar cells), reversibly transitions to a cubic α -phase at 57 °C. In the case of CsPbI₃ the RT stable yellow, orthorhombic non-perovskite δ -phase, transitions above 305 °C to a phase meta-stable, black, cubic perovskite α -phase. In the case of CsPbI₃ it is the α -phase that shows the best photovoltaic performance.^{20, 23} Upon cooling, the phase metastable α -CsPbI₃ transitions to less symmetrical tetragonal β - and orthorhombic distorted perovskite γ -phases.²⁴

In contrast, CPs show a high phase stability in the range from RT to ~ 400 °C. In the case of the BaZrS₃ and BaHfS₃ the RT stable phase is the orthorhombic distorted perovskite (DP) phase. Upon heating to $\sim 510 - 530$ °C, BaZrS₃ and $\sim 410 - 430$ °C, BaHfS₃ reversibly transition to a more symmetric tetragonal phase.¹³ In the case of SrZrS₃ and SrHfS₃ the thermodynamically most stable phase at RT is the non-perovskite NL phase.²⁵ However, depending on the experimental conditions, the compositions can also be prepared in the form of a phase meta-stable DP phase.²⁶ While the conversion of meta-stable DP phase to stable NL phase is reversible, the conversion temperatures are quite high; e.g., 750 °C in the case of SrZrS₃.^{26a} Theoretical modeling suggests that SrZrS₃ can also form a more symmetric cubic phase at temperatures > 1200 °C.²⁷ Third, within the temperature range relevant for the optoelectronic applications the HPs form symmetric (cubic or tetragonal) phases. Within the same temperature range the CPs studied here form lower symmetry orthorhombic phases. Significant energy must be delivered to the lattice to transiently produce higher symmetry tetragonal or cubic phases.

Experimental observations discussed qualitatively above correlate with the available thermodynamic data. We first consider the stability of the HPs and CPs with respect to the decomposition into their binary constituents, expressed as formation reaction shown in Eq. (5):

As noted in previous sections, the analysis by Senocrate et al.,²⁸ showed that, although the $\Delta_{\text{f}}H^{\circ}(\text{MAPbI}_3)$ is slightly positive, thanks to the entropic contributions, above the room temperature, the free energy of reaction (5) is predicted to be negative. Thus, the decomposition of MAPbI₃ to MAI and PbI₂ is thermodynamically likely an unfavorable process, which is supported by various experimental observations.²⁸ Similarly, CsPbI₃ was found to be thermodynamically slightly favored over its constituent binary halides with $\Delta_{\text{f}}H^{\circ}(\alpha\text{-CsPbI}_3) = -2.83 \pm 0.9$ kJ/mol.²⁹ While the experimental thermodynamic data are not available for the CPs, an estimate is available from theoretical calculations.^{26b, 30} In a recent study, Yu et al.^{26b} reported calculated enthalpies of formation (at 0K) from binary precursors for a series of CPs studied experimentally in our work: $\Delta_{\text{f}}H^{\circ}(\text{BaZrS}_3) = -49.5$ kJ/mol, $\Delta_{\text{f}}H^{\circ}(\text{BaHfS}_3) = -46.1$ kJ/mol, $\Delta_{\text{f}}H^{\circ}(\text{SrZrS}_3) = -20.8$ kJ/mol, $\Delta_{\text{f}}H^{\circ}(\text{SrHfS}_3) = -13.6$ kJ/mol. These values suggest that the CPs studied here are even more stable with respect to decomposition into binary compounds than MAPbI₃ or CsPbI₃. This is consistent with our high-temperature XRD studies under air free atmosphere, where all studied CPs show no sign of decomposition up to 700 °C (SI Fig. S4).

In earlier work Navrotsky et al.,^{29, 31} showed that for perovskites the variations in $\Delta_{\text{f}}H^{\circ}$ can be related to two key factors, strength of the B-X bond, as expressed by its dissociation energy and the lattice structure expressed by Goldschmidt's tolerance factor, t_{F} . For the compounds studied in this work, a comparison of bond dissociation energies shows that the metal chalcogen bonds are nearly three times stronger than the Pb-I bond ($D_0(\text{Pb-I}) = 197$ kJ/mol, $D_0(\text{Zr-S}) = 546$ kJ/mol, $D_0(\text{Hf-S}) = 558$ kJ/mol).^{32, 33} Thus, we attribute the increased stability of the CPs primarily to the higher strength of the chalcogen sulfur bond. As originally pointed out by Pauling,³⁴ two factors mainly influencing the strength of a chemical bond are the difference in electronegativities and the extent of the orbital overlap between the atoms forming the bond. While the electronegativities of sulfur and iodine are comparable ($\chi(\text{S}) = 2.58$, $\chi(\text{I}) = 2.66$), due to the relatively high electronegativity of lead ($\chi(\text{Pb}) = 2.33$) and low electronegativities of Zr and Hf

Figure 8. Enthalpy of reaction (5) as a function of tolerance factor, t_{F} , for a series of halide, chalcogenide, and oxide perovskites. Also included are the heats of formation for the non-perovskite, needle-like crystal phases of CsPbI₃ and ternary chalcogenides. Theoretically calculated values (at 0K) are indicated by a star. In cases when only one phase is shown, it is the phase stable at room temperature.

($\chi(\text{Zr}) = 1.33$, $\chi(\text{Hf}) = 1.3$), the chalcogenide bonds have much more ionic character than the Pb-I bond. In addition, sulfur generally forms much stronger bonds than iodine thanks to a significant participation of its p - orbitals. Iodine, on the other hand, forms weaker bonds as it has larger, more diffuse orbitals that result in less effective overlap. Since the bond length decreases with increasing bond energy,³⁵ the chalcogenide bonds are shorter than the Pb-I bond. Thus, the increase in the strength of the metal-chalcogen bond also explains much more compact structure of the CPs, relative to the HPs, as shown in Scheme 1.

In Fig. 8 we show a plot of the dependence of $\Delta_{\text{f}}H^{\circ}$ on t_{F} for a series of halide, oxide and chalcogenide perovskites, using the literature data.^{26b, 36} Also included are the known heats of formation for the non-perovskite, needle-like crystal phases of CsPbI₃ and ternary chalcogenides.^{26b, 37} Consistent with the prior studies,²⁹ we find that just like for oxides and HPs also for CPs the $\Delta_{\text{f}}H^{\circ}$ decreases systematically with increasing t_{F} ; i.e., increase in t_{F} increases the perovskite stability. The $\Delta_{\text{f}}H^{\circ}$ values for CaZrS₃ and CaHfS₃, which have the lowest t_{F} of the series, are positive, which is consistent with the observation that these ternary chalcogenides are experimentally difficult to prepare.²² The Sr²⁺ compounds, for which $t_{\text{F}} > 0.9$ are stable as ternary compositions, however, their most thermodynamically favorable crystal phase is the non-perovskite needle-like phase. For the Ba²⁺, the tolerance factor increases to $t_{\text{F}} > 0.95$. Both compositions are stable as ternary compounds, and their thermodynamically most favorable phase is a DP orthorhombic phase. As we have shown in our recent theoretical studies,^{13, 27} upon heating to sufficiently high temperatures, the orthorhombic DP lattices of SrZrS₃ and BaZrS₃ can be sufficiently “softened” so that the increased thermal motion can eliminate the octahedral distortions and the lattice transitions to the more symmetric tetragonal or even cubic arrangement. The onset of this process is experimentally observed at ~ 510 °C for BaZrS₃ and ~ 410 °C for BaHfS₃. In addition to the general structural factors, entropic terms, such as phonon modes associated with the A-site cation can play a significant role in determining the phase stability of the CPs. Theoretical study by

Yu et al.,^{26b} suggests that these phonon modes are primarily responsible for the stabilization of the DP phases of SrZrS₃ and SrHfS₃ over the NL phases, at temperatures above 700 °C. As a result, the two compounds can be prepared at lower temperatures in stable NL phase and at higher temperatures, with rapid reaction quenching, in the meta-stable DP phase.

While direct decomposition of MAPbI₃ via reaction (5) is likely thermodynamically unfavorable, according to the analysis by Senocrate et al.,²⁸ reactions (1a) and (1b) can be favorable in the absence of air even at room temperature and are quite favorable in the presence of oxygen. Thus, the thermodynamic data suggest that the primary instability of the MAPbI₃ is associated with its organic cation. This is consistent with our TGA results and prior TGA studies, as well as other more recent experimental studies,³⁸ which show that the degradation of MAPbI₃ in the 250 – 290 °C temperature is associated with the loss of organic A-cation primarily via the reactions (1a) and (1b), depending on specific experimental conditions. In the 400 – 600 °C temperature range, the decomposition of the HPs has been attributed primarily to the sublimation of the PbI₂.^{18, 20} As shown Dastidar et al.,²⁰ the onsets of the PbI₂ sublimation and the CsPbI₃ thermal decomposition (attributed to partial PbI₂ loss) are observed approximately at the same temperature. Relatively low temperature at which the sublimation losses are observed suggests that in both structures the PbI₂ is weakly bound within the PbI₆ octahedra of their respective crystal lattices. In the presence of oxygen, the PbI₂ can rapidly oxidize to PbO or other oxides via the reaction (1d), which is thermodynamically favorable ($\Delta_r H^\circ = -43.5$ kJ/mol) even at room temperature.³⁹

Based on the above analysis, the higher thermal stability of CPs, can be, in part, attributed to the absence of organic components in their structure. In addition, while the experimental data on the sublimation temperature of ZrS₂ or HfS₂ are not readily available, our TGA results show no evidence of mass losses typically associated with sublimation. Also, high temperature XRD studies (SI Fig. S4) show no changes in phase composition, that could suggest sublimation at least up to 700 °C. Thus, unlike halides, CPs do not seem to be susceptible to sublimation of its constituents before they undergo oxidation. We attribute this to a much higher dissociation energies of the Zr-S and Hf-S bonds compared to the Pb-I bond, as discussed in previous paragraphs. An interesting aspect of the thermal stability of CPs is their susceptibility to oxidation. As noted above, direct oxidation of CPs (e.g., reaction (3a), $\Delta_r H^\circ_{298} = -1093$ kJ/mol) is thermodynamically much more favorable than the oxidation of PbI₂. This is mainly due to high affinity of Zr and Hf towards oxidation ($\Delta_r H^\circ_{298}(\text{ZrO}_2) = -1097.5$ kJ/mol, $\Delta_r H^\circ_{298}(\text{HfO}_2) = -1144.7$ kJ/mol).⁴⁰ Yet, the oxidation of CPs studied here is not experimentally observed up to at least 450 °C. We propose that this surprisingly high stability of CPs may be caused by a formation of a thin passivating oxide layer on their surface. Evidence for formation of such layer on the surface of CP powders was noted in our previous work¹⁵ and more recently in studies of sputtered BaZrS₃ films.⁴¹ Further studies are needed to confirm the formation and the exact role of the CP oxide passivating layer.

Finally, we would like to note that from the standpoint of impact of thermal stress on the performance of CPs in optoelectronic applications, the results our study provide only a partial picture. For example, as was shown in earlier studies of the MAPbI₃ and other HP-based solar cells,⁴² thermal cycling of encapsulated devices through a relative modest temperature range of -30 to 85 °C leads to a rapid degradation of their performance, with no or small changes observed in the XRD

patterns of the HPs after the cycling. As shown in Fig. 7, cycling of the MAPbI₃ through the -30 to 85 °C temperature range is expected to result in repeated transition between its tetragonal and cubic phases. Lack of notable changes in the XRD patterns during the cycling suggest that such changes are reversible without a significant chemical degradation taking place in the process. Yet, a nearly complete degradation of the device performance is observed within several hundred cycles. This was attributed to a combination of thermally induced changes in the HP film morphology, grain sizes, surface properties and defects.⁴² These and similar results show that even at temperatures significantly lower than the thermal degradation temperatures of materials identified in the present work, thermal stress can dramatically impact the performance of devices. Therefore, a full assessment of the application potential of CPs will require in-situ studies of the performance of devices under a thermal stress and/or use of experimental approaches that can provide simultaneously information about the effect of thermal stress on the structure and electronic properties of the materials.^{42a, 43}

CONCLUSIONS

We have synthesized two ternary halides (MAPbI₃, CsPbI₃), four perovskite (BaZrS₃, β -SrZrS₃, BaHfS₃, SrHfS₃) and two non-perovskite (α -SrZrS₃ and α -EuZrS₃) ternary chalcogenides and investigated their thermal stability in the temperature range from 25 to 800 °C, in air using TGA, room- and high-temperature XRD and diffuse reflectance spectroscopies. We showed that halides and chalcogenides behave differently under thermal stress. Consistent with previous reports, our results show that at room temperature, MAPbI₃ is most stable in tetragonal perovskite phase and CsPbI₃ in non-perovskite needle-like crystal phase. Upon heating to 50 – 60 °C (MAPbI₃) or 300 – 310 °C (CsPbI₃) the halides reversibly transition to a more symmetric cubic phase. When heated in air, halides chemically decompose in multiple steps. MAPbI₃ starts decomposing at ~250 – 290 °C. Based on earlier studies, this is attributed to a degradation and loss of its organic cation. The next step, starting in both halides at ~400 °C, is attributed to the loss of PbI₂, primarily via sublimation. Any remaining PbI₂ is oxidized to lead oxides. Chalcogenide perovskites form at room temperature phases with lower symmetry, but these show higher phase stability as well as chemical stability. Ba²⁺ salts, BaZrS₃ and BaHf₃, form at room temperature stable, distorted perovskite (orthorhombic, *Pnma*) phases. Upon heating to 410 – 430 °C (BaHfS₃) and 510 – 530 °C (BaZrS₃) they reversibly transition to a more symmetric tetragonal phase. In the case of Sr salts, SrZrS₃ and SrHf₃, the thermodynamically most stable phase at room temperature is the non-perovskite needle-like phase (orthorhombic, *Pnma*). However, when prepared at temperatures above ~700 °C both compounds can be isolated as a meta-stable distorted perovskite phase. The transition between the two phases is reversible. All studied ternary chalcogenides are chemically stable up to ~450 °C. Above this temperature they rapidly oxidize with the final products of the oxidation being a sulphate (ASO₄) and dioxide (BO₂). At 100 °C in air, CPs show no signs of degradation in XRD or optical measurements for period of at least one week. Further studies of CPs at the device level are needed to determine whether the chalcogenide perovskites can indeed be effectively exploited in photovoltaics and optoelectronics.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Materials: The starting materials were BaZrO₃ (99%, Alfa Aesar), SrZrO₃ (99.3%, Alfa Aesar), Eu₂O₃ (99.99%), ZrO₂ (Pure, Soviet

Union), HfO₂ (99.95%, Alfa Aesar), Eu₂O₃ (99.99%), BaCO₃ (pure, Lachema), SrCO₃ (99.9%, Sigma Aldrich), S (99.98%, Sigma Aldrich), B (98%, Alfa Aesar), Methylamine (40 wt% aqueous solution, Acros Organics), HI (57 wt% aqueous solution, stabilized, Acros Organics), PbI₂ (99%, Acros Organics), CsI (99.9%, Acros Organics).

Syntheses of halide perovskites: See supporting information section 14 for safety considerations when working with Pb-containing compounds. MAPbI₃ was synthesized in two-steps. In the first step, MAI was prepared by a dropwise addition of 0.290 ml (3.145 mmol) 40 wt% aqueous solution of methylamine to an excess (~0.830 ml, 6.28 mmol) of HI cooled in ice bath. The mixture was stirred in an ice bath for 2 hrs. and then allowed to stand in open container without stirring at room temperature overnight (~12 hrs.). Diethyl ether was added into the solution until white powder was formed. This powder was separated from solvent by vacuum filtration. The product was purified by recrystallization from ethanol. In the second step, 0.47 g (2.97 mmol) of MAI and 1.37 g (2.97 mmol) of PbI₂ were dissolved in 10 ml of stirred dimethylformamide at 70 °C. After complete dissolution of the powders, the solvent was slowly evaporated at 110 °C. The resulting black powder was stored in an argon-filled glovebox. CsPbI₃ was prepared by dissolving 0.36 g (1.38 mmol) of CsI and 0.64 g (1.38 mmol) PbI₂ in 10 ml of DMSO at 70 °C with vigorous stirring. The temperature was then increased to 80 °C to evaporate the solvent. The resulting yellow powder was stored under argon.

Syntheses of ternary oxides: In a typical reaction, first, 2.3-2.8 g of BaCO₃ or SrCO₃ (ACO₃) was mixed with equimolar amount of HfO₂ and 10 ml of isopropyl alcohol. The paste was ground in an agate mortar for 15 min., air dried and ground again for 5 min. The ground powder was then transferred in a ceramic boat into a furnace. The furnace was heated to 1100 °C, with a heating rate of 10 °C/min, and held at this temperature for 16 hrs. The heating was then discontinued, and the furnace was allowed to cool down to room temperature.

Syntheses of ternary chalcogenides: In a typical reaction, 1-2 g of ABO₃ ternary oxide was mixed with boron and sulfur in molar ratio 1:2.2:3 (ABO₃:B:S) and 5 ml of isopropyl alcohol, were ground in an agate mortar for 10 – 15 min. The solvent was allowed to evaporate during grinding. Well ground dry powder was transferred to a 15 mm i.d. quartz tube. The tube was connected to a Schlenk line and evacuated at < 0.5 Pa for 30 min. During the evacuation the bottom section of the tube containing the reaction mixture was immersed in a water bath heated to 70 °C to remove any residual moisture from the tube and the sample. The tube was then flame sealed under vacuum. The typical length of the sealed ampule was ~13 cm. During the flame sealing, the part of the tube containing the reagents was immersed in a cold-water bath to prevent the reaction mixture heating from the sealing torch. The sealed reaction ampule with the reagents was transferred into a temperature calibrated furnace where it was heated according to a predefined heating program. In a typical reaction, the mixture was heated at a ramp rate of 5 °C/min to 300 °C, held at this temperature for 5 hrs., then again heated at a ramp rate of 5 °C/min to 600 °C and held at this temperature for 5 hrs. In the final step the reaction mixture was heated to 1000 °C/36 h in the case of DP phases, 950 °C/240 h for α-EuZrS₃ and 800 °C /60 h for α-SrZrS₃. The cooling rate was 5 °C/min. After the cool down, the ampules were opened at ambient conditions. The product removed from the reaction ampule was transferred into a beaker with ~20 mL of HPLC-grade methanol and sonicated for 10 min. to remove any soluble byproducts (e.g., B₂O₃). The product was then isolated by vacuum filtration, air dried and stored in glass vial in air at room temperature.

Structural characterization. XRD diffraction studies were performed on the as-synthesized materials, as well as on the materials after thermal analysis and after short-term and long-term stability

studies. The diffraction patterns were collected using Panalytical Empyrean diffractometer (Netherlands) with Cu K α radiation in the Bragg-Brentano geometry.

High-temperature XRD measurement was performed on Panalytical Empyrean diffractometer coupled with Anton Paar high-temperature chamber HTK-16N using Pt heating strip in air. The patterns were collected every 10 °C, with data collection time of 60 seconds. During the data collection the temperature was held constant. The heating rate between the measurements was 8 °C/min. After cooling, the XRD pattern of each sample was collected again to identify possible phase transformations during cooling.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy-dispersive X-ray spectra (EDS) were obtained on cold-pressed pellets using dual-beam scanning electron microscope combined with a high current focused ion beam (FIB) - FEI Quanta 3D 200i equipped with EDS AMETEK. SEM images of the surface morphology of the pellets were recorded at a magnification of 4000x. EDS spectra were collected at several locations evenly distributed across the entire pellet with accelerating voltage of 30 kV, emission current of 0.1 nA and working distance of 10 mm.

Electronic structure characterization. Diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded on Jasco V-770 (UV-Vis/NIR) spectrophotometer equipped with a reflectance accessory ARSN-917. Data were collected in the range 250-2000 nm with a scan rate of 1000 nm/min with resolution of 2 nm. Prior to the measurement the powders were pressed into pellets with a pressure of ~100 MPa. The baseline for all the experiments was obtained by a manufacturer provided Spectralon standard.

Thermal analysis (TGA) was performed with Linseis STA1600, (Linseis Messgeraete GmbH, Germany) with a heating rate of 8 °C/min or 1 °C/min in air. The DTA traces were recorded with an empty Al₂O₃ crucible as a reference.

Long-term thermal stability tests were carried out by storing the ternary chalcogenides in ceramic boats in the box furnace heated at 100 °C in air, for one week. Small amount of each compound was removed every 24 hours and characterized by XRD.

Short-term thermal stability test was performed on Panalytical Empyrean diffractometer coupled with Anton Paar high-temperature chamber HTK-16N using Pt heating strip in air. The XRD patterns were collected at 100, 300, and 500 °C, every 10 min for 1 hr. The collection time at each collection point was 120 s. The heating rate between the isothermal segments was 8 °C/min. After cooling, the XRD pattern of each sample was collected again to identify possible phase transformations during cooling.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

Structural characteristics of MAPbI₃, CsPbI₃, BaZrS₃, β-SrZrS₃, BaHfS₃ and SrHfS₃. XRD, TGA, short-term thermal stability and diffuse reflectance characterization of α-SrZrS₃ and α-EuZrS₃. EDS spectra of CPs and TGA of the CPs measured at 1 °C/min. Tauc plot of all prepared ternary chalcogenides. This material is available free of charge via the internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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Materials synthesis, visualization, manuscript editing. P.H. Materials characterization, data analysis, visualization, manuscript editing. M.S. Conceptualization, funding acquisition, project administration, original manuscript writing, data analysis, visualization, editing.

Notes. The authors declare no competing financial interests.

■ ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 810701 and by the Slovak Research and Development Agency under grant agreement no. APVV-19-410. SKT acknowledges partial support from project USCCCOR (ZöNFP: NFP313020BUZ3), co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund within the Operational Programme Integrated Infrastructure.

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Synopsis. Phase and chemical changes induced by thermal stress were investigated for two ternary halides ($MAPbI_3$, $CsPbI_3$), four perovskite ($BaZrS_3$, β - $SrZrS_3$, $BaHfS_3$, $SrHfS_3$) and two non-perovskite (α - $SrZrS_3$ and α - $EuZrS_3$) ternary chalcogenides in the temperature range from 25 to 800 °C, in air, using TGA, room- and high-temperature XRD and diffuse reflectance spectroscopies. Ternary chalcogenides show distinctly higher phase and chemical stability within the studied temperature range. The structural origins of the observed differences are discussed.